

Peptide Models for the Metal-Binding Sites of Proteins and Enzymes

BIBUDHENDRA SARKAR

The Research Institute of the Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, M5G 1X8
and
The Department of Biochemistry, University of Toronto, Toronto, M5S 1A8,
Ontario, Canada

A series of peptide models were utilized to probe the metal-binding sites of proteins and enzymes. Studies with three peptide analogues, GlyGly-L-His, GlyGly-L-His-NHCH₃, and L-Asp-L-Ala-L-His-NHCH₃, representing the Cu(II)-transport site of human serum albumin revealed that the Cu(II)-binding site is located at the NH₂-terminal of the protein involving the α -NH₂, imidazole, and two deprotonated peptide nitrogens and the COO⁻ of the Asp residue forming a pentacoordinated structure. Similarly, the investigation of the Ni(II)-transport site of human serum albumin using peptide models revealed the structure of the Ni(II)-binding site of albumin. A cyclic octapeptide, cyclo(Gly-L-Glu-Gly-Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly), was designed to mimic the Zn(II)-binding site of carboxypeptidase. Structural studies with the cyclic octapeptide showed that the Zn(II) binding took place with the imidazoles of the two histidine residues and the carboxyl side chain of the glutamic acid residue, a finding similar to what is known about the Zn(II)-binding sites of carboxypeptidase. Furthermore, a cyclic heptapeptide, cyclo(Gly-L-His-L-Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly), was designed to mimic the Zn(II)-binding site of carbonic anhydrase. Detailed studies with the cyclic heptapeptide showed that Zn(II) bound to this peptide involving imidazoles from all the three histidine residues as is known to be the case for the Zn(II)-binding site of carbonic anhydrase. Considerations for successful design of peptide models as well as its limitations are discussed.

IMPORTANT advances have been made in recent years in the investigations of metal protein interactions in which the peptide models have played a very significant role. Small peptide molecules designed to mimic the metal binding sites of proteins and enzymes can provide valuable information which is otherwise difficult to obtain from the studies of the native molecules. Models for metal binding sites which are located on a short polypeptide chain may be designed using a linear peptide molecule with suitable side chains positioned in strategic locations. However, models to mimic the metal-binding sites originating from different parts of the polypeptide chain such as those found in most metalloenzymes and metalloproteins are difficult to design. In this case, a linear peptide may not be suitable. Cyclic peptides with side chains suitably positioned for the purpose of metal binding may provide both the rigidity and the ligand binding geometry of the native proteins and enzymes.

We have designed peptide models mimicking both types of metal-binding sites discussed above. In this article, I shall discuss some of our results with Cu(II) and Ni(II)-transport sites of human serum albumin and the Zn(II)-binding sites of two metalloenzymes: carboxypeptidase and carbonic anhydrase.

Copper(II)-transport site of human serum albumin:

Copper(II) bound to albumin is considered to be the transport form of Cu(II) in blood. It has

long been known that bovine serum albumin has one strong binding site for Cu(II)^{1,2}. The stoichiometry of Cu(II) binding to HSA* was established by us later³. The involvement of α -NH₂ at the strong Cu(II)-binding site was shown by blocking the reaction of the α -NH₂ group with 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene by Cu(II)⁴. Titrimetric studies indicated that one of the coordinating groups at the binding site had a pK_a near 8⁵. The 525 nm absorption band of the 1:1 Cu(II)-albumin complex and the displacement of two protons by the first Cu(II) at pH 9 suggested that two peptide bond nitrogens and a possible fourth coordinating atom such as an imidazole nitrogen participated along with the α -NH₂ at the strong site⁶. Subsequently, we found that dog serum albumin failed to exhibit the characteristics of a specific first binding site for Cu(II)⁷. Amino acid sequence analysis of the NH₂-terminal region of DSA showed that the third residue histidine, critical to the binding of Cu(II), has been replaced with a tyrosine residue⁸. This finding confirmed the involvement of the imidazole nitrogen in the coordination of Cu(II) in the case of HSA and BSA.

On the basis of the proposed Cu(II)-binding site of albumin involving the α -amino nitrogen, two intervening peptide nitrogens and the imidazole nitrogen of the histidine residue in the third position, three peptide analogues were designed and synthesized. The peptide glycylglycyl-L-histidine was synthesized by active ester method^{9,10}. Another

*Abbreviations used: HSA, human serum albumin; BSA, bovine serum albumin; DSA, dog serum albumin; GGH, glycylglycyl-L-histidine; GGHNMA, glycylglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide; AAHNMA, L-aspartyl-L-alanyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide.

peptide analogue was prepared by derivatizing the carboxyl group to N-methyl amide to more closely resemble the protein molecule¹¹. Finally, the native sequence peptide, L-aspartyl-L-alanyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide, representing the Cu(II) transport site of HSA, was synthesized employing the N-hydroxysuccinimide ester method¹².

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF LOG STABILITY CONSTANTS (LOG β_{pqr} , LOG β'_{pqr} and LOG β''_{pqr}) OF THE COMPLEX SPECIES $M_pH_qA_r$ [$M = \text{Cu(II)}$, $A = \text{GLYGLY-L-HIS-N-METHYLAMIDE}$, $A' = \text{GLYGLY-L-HIS}$, $A'' = \text{L-ASP-L-ALA-L-HIS-N-METHYLAMIDE}$] IN 0.15 M NaCl AT 25°

p	q	r	log β_{pqr} ($M_pH_qA_r$)	log β'_{pqr} (M_pH_qA')	log β''_{pqr} (M_pH_qA'')
0	3	1	—	17.50	17.267
0	2	1	14.47	14.78	14.286
0	1	1	8.00	8.04	7.731
1	-2	1	-0.479	-1.99	-0.55

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL PROPERTIES OF THE Cu(II)-TRANSPORT SITE OF HUMAN SERUM ALBUMIN, Cu(II)-COMPLEXES OF THE NATIVE SEQUENCE PEPTIDE, AND THE DESIGNED PEPTIDES

Cu(II) complex	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ_{max} (liter. mol ⁻¹ . cm ⁻¹)
Human serum albumin-Cu(II)	525	101
GlyGly-L-His-Cu(II) ($MH_{2.5}A$)	525	103
GlyGly-L-His-NHMe-Cu(II) ($MH_{2.5}A$)	525	103
L-Asp-L-Ala-L-His-NHMe-Cu(II) ($MH_{2.5}A$)	525	103

TABLE 3—PARAMAGNETIC RESONANCE PARAMETERS OF Cu(II) ION FOR ITS FIRST COMPLEX WITH HUMAN SERUM ALBUMIN, GLY-GLY-L-HIS-NHCH₃ AND L-ASP-L-ALA-L-HIS-NHCH₃ AT 77K

Ligand compound	pH	$g_{\parallel}$	$g_{\perp}$	$A_{\parallel}$ (gauss)	$A_{\perp}$ (mk)
Human serum albumin	6.5	2.166	2.051	214	21.6
Human serum albumin	9.2	2.169	2.049	214	21.6
Gly-Gly-L-His-NHCH ₃	6.4	2.17	2.051	211	21.3
Gly-Gly-L-His-NHCH ₃	11.2	2.163	2.051	209	21.1
L-Asp-L-Ala-L-His-NHCH ₃	6.5	2.167	2.050	211	21.4
L-Asp-L-Ala-L-His-NHCH ₃	11.1	2.166	2.049	209	21.1

aA (mk) = 0.046686 gA (gauss)

The Cu(II) complex equilibria in the systems containing Cu(II) and the peptides were studied by analytical potentiometry^{13,14}. The species and their stability constants are presented in Table 1. In all the systems studied, there is one major species ($MH_{2.5}A$) existing in physiological pH. The spectral properties of the major Cu(II)-peptide species are almost identical to HSA-Cu(II) (Table 2). The crystal of Cu(II)-GGHNMA was prepared at physiological pH and its molecular structure was determined. It is shown in Fig. 1 that Cu(II) is tetradentately chelated by amino-terminal nitrogen, the next two peptide nitrogens and the histidyl nitrogen of a single tripeptide molecule in a slightly distorted square-planar arrangement¹⁵. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectra of the synthetic peptides correspond very well with those

for the Cu(II)-HSA complex¹⁶. The results are shown in Table 3. At 77 K, the epr spectra of Cu(II) complex of HSA exhibited only one form of epr signal between pH 6.5 and 9.5. The presence of equally spaced nine-line superhyperfine structure with spacing ~15 gauss indicated considerable covalent bonding between Cu(II) and four nitrogen atoms derived from the protein. In the pH range between 6 and 11, the epr spectra of Cu(II) complexes of AAHNMA and GGHNMA also exhibited well resolved nine-line superhyperfine structure.

Fig. 1. Structure of the Cu(II)-complex of the designed peptide glycyglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide by X-ray crystallographic analysis¹⁵.

All the above studies showed a considerable similarity between AAHNMA and GGHNMA. However, the native sequence peptide AAHNMA resembled closer to the protein HSA as far as their Cu(II)-binding affinity and dissociation are concerned¹⁷. This raised the question as to whether the Cu(II)-binding site indeed involved the side chain carboxyl group in addition to the four nitrogen ligands already proposed. In order to solve this question, a detailed investigation was undertaken with ¹³C-nmr technique¹⁸.

The consequences of the binding of a paramagnetic metal such as Cu(II) by a ligand molecule are alterations of the chemical shifts and linewidths of the nuclear resonances of the ligand. But Cu(II) has a long electron spin relaxation time ($T_1 \sim 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Because of this, its dominant effect is line broadening. The broadening of line is caused by the considerable decrease of the relaxation time due to the localized magnetic field of species bearing an unpaired electron in the proximity of the nmr active nucleus. The dipolar term is usually dominant in many cases. But the scalar term which corresponds to the transfers of unpaired spin density from the metal ion to the carbon is also quite significant. If the dipolar term dominates the line broadening, the ratio of $T_1/T_2 = 7/6$. If, however, the scalar mechanism is important, $T_1/T_2 > 7/6$. In this

instance, it is possible to interpret the data in terms of actual binding of paramagnetic metal with the ligand from the line broadening results.

TABLE 4—CARBON-13 SPIN-LATTICE AND TRANSVERSE RELAXATION TIMES IN PRESENCE OF Cu(II)

[Cu(II)/peptide molar ratio 1 : 50, pH = 7.0, $\omega_1 = 25.16$ MHz, $\omega_2 = 90.54$ MHz].

	T_1 1p s^{-1}	T_2 2p s^{-1}	T_{1p}/T_{2p}	$T_{2p\omega_1}/T_{2p\omega_2}$
Asp COO ⁻		31		1.5
C ₃	0.26	375	1440	1.6
C ₄		280		1.6
C ₅	0.30	230	770	1.8
Asp C _α	0.37	22	60	1.3
Asp C _β	0.40	67	170	2.3
His C _β	0.28	31	110	1.9

The observed T_1 and T_2 values for AAHNMA-Cu(II) are given in Table 4 at pH 7.0 for a Cu(II)/peptide molar ratio of 1 : 50. For all of the carbon atoms which are affected by Cu(II), the ratio $T_1/T_2 \gg \gg 7/6$ indicates predominant scalar interactions. The lack of any frequency dependencies of the linewidth in Cu(II)-containing solution

Fig. 2. ^{13}C -NMR spectra (25.16. MHz) of D_2O solution containing 0.27 M L-aspartyl-L-alanyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide and 5.41×10^{-3} M Cu(II). The pH of solutions was (a) 2.0, (b) 7.0 and (c) 10.0 ("corresponds to Asp COO⁻").

indicated that fast exchange limit was obtained in all the cases. Coordination of Cu(II) with the peptide showed a large line broadening for several ^{13}C resonances, especially C₃, C₄ and C₅ of the His, Asp C_β, Asp COO⁻, and His C_β (Fig. 2). The results suggest that in addition to four nitrogen ligands (one amino, two peptide and one imidazole nitrogen) in a square-planar coordination, there is the involvement of the side chain carboxyl group forming a pentacoordinated structure (Fig. 3). Further investigation of Cu(II) interaction of the NH₂-terminal 24-residue peptide fragment of HSA by ^{13}C -nmr technique confirmed the proposed structure¹⁹⁻²².

Fig. 3. Structure of the Cu(II)-transport site¹⁹.

Nickel-transport site of human serum albumin :

Nickel(II) in human serum is mainly associated with albumin and L-histidine²³. Nickel(II), like Cu(II), blocks the reaction of 1-fluoro-2,4-dinitrobenzene with the α -amino group at the NH₂-terminus of BSA. It has also been shown in preliminary tests that increasing amounts of Ni(II) caused the characteristic purple colour of the 1 : 1 Cu(II)-BSA complex to fade and change to yellow⁶. These results suggest that Ni(II) binds at the NH₂-terminal region of albumin. Further experiments in this laboratory showed that HSA possesses a strong binding site for Ni(II)²⁴.

In order to investigate the nature of the Ni(II)-binding site of HSA, detailed studies were undertaken with the synthetic native sequence peptide AAHNMA. In studying the Cu(II) binding to AAHNMA, it was found that the proton-liberation

Fig. 4. Species distribution for the Ni(II)-L-aspartyl-L-alanyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide system as a function of pH. [Ni(II)] = 1.09×10^{-4} M; [Peptide] = 4.474×10^{-4} M. Curve 1, MA ($\log \beta_{101} = 5.50$); Curve 2, MA₂ ($\log \beta_{102} = 11.56$); Curve 3, MH₋₁A₂ ($\log \beta_{1-21} = 5.94$); Curve 4, MH₋₂A₂ ($\log \beta_{1-22} = 4.75$)²⁴.

reaction begins at a pH slightly above 5 and a rapid increase in $\delta H^+/\delta C_M$ occurs to a maximum of almost 3.5 at pH 6.4. This rapid displacement is attributed to the formation of the major species $MH_{-2}A$ (Fig. 4). At pH 9.5-10.0, $\delta H^+/\delta C_M$ is steady at a value of 2, where the species $MH_{-2}A$ is present exclusively. Since in this pH range the β -carboxyl, imidazole and amino groups are already titrated, the protons liberated can be attributed to complex formation by the two peptide amide groups.

The visible spectra of Ni(II) complexes of HSA and AAHNMA are very similar. Analysis of the spectra of HSA as a function of pH, in the presence of 1 equivalent of Ni(II), showed that the spectrum of hexaquo-Ni(II) with absorption maxima at 395 and at 650-720 nm (broad doublet) changes rapidly with increasing pH to a highly absorbing peak at 420 nm, indicative of a square-planar or square-pyramidal geometry about the metal ion (Fig. 5). By pH 6.9, the peak has developed well with a shoulder in the region of 450-480 nm. At higher pH, the increases in absorption are less, but a small peak develops at 240 nm.

Fig. 5. Visible absorption spectra as a function of pH for the Ni(II)-human serum albumin system. $[Ni(II)-HSA] = 1.01 \text{ mM}$ in 0.15 M NaCl , 1 cm cell path with protein as reference at 25°C .

The visible absorption spectra of Ni(II)-AAHNMA are shown in Fig. 6. At pH 3.5, a spectrum of hexaquo-Ni(II) is observed. When the pH is increased to approximately 5.1, the spectrum is shifted to a λ_{max} of 385 nm and a broad peak at about 640 nm. It is possible that some initial carboxylate interaction with Ni(II) before proton liberation may be taking place, yielding a complex of octahedral symmetry. By pH 5.4, the peak maximum has shifted to 415 nm and the solution is a mixture of octahedral Ni(II) and mainly the highly absorbing MA complex ($\lambda_{max} = 428 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon_{max} = 202$). As the pH is increased, the absorption at 420 nm increases sharply, coinciding with the increases in the species $MH_{-2}A$ ($\lambda_{max} = 420$, $\epsilon_{max} = 135$) as shown in the species distribution. A shoulder in the region 450-480 nm is also present on the high

wavelength side of the 420 nm peak. The results are very similar to those observed with Ni(II)-HSA.

Fig. 6. Visible absorption spectra as a function of pH for the Ni(II)-L-aspartyl-L-alanyl-L-histidyl-N-methylamide system. $[Ni(II)] = 10.97 \text{ mM}$; $[Peptide] = 50 \text{ mM}$ in 0.15 M NaCl at 25°C .

These results strongly suggest that the Ni(II)-binding site is located in the NH_2 -terminal tripeptide segment of HSA. Further studies with Ni(II)-binding to DSA and its NH_2 -terminal model peptide glycylglycyl-L-tyrosine-N-methyl amide showed a lack of binding specificity²². There is a histidine residue in the third position of HSA as has been discussed before and it has a greater specificity for Ni(II)-binding. Hence, it appears that the imidazole group is involved in the Ni(II)-binding.

To further characterize this site, detailed 1H - and ^{13}C -nmr experiments were undertaken with Ni(II)-binding to AAHNMA²⁶. The individual chemical shifts ($\Delta = \delta_{1/1 \text{ complex}} - \delta_{free \text{ peptide}}$) for carbons and protons are shown in Fig. 7. The Asp COO^- carbon is affected most of all by Ni(II) binding ($\Delta = 8.32 \text{ ppm}$ at $pH = 9.1$) which is consistent with carboxylate-Ni(II) coordination. The imidazole ring system also shows large variations [$C(5)$, $\Delta = -2.45 \text{ ppm}$]. Upon complexation, the Ni(II)-binding to the NH_2 -terminal and COO^- group affects the α carbon (4.69 ppm) more strongly while in the case of β carbon, we observed a shielding effect (-1.73 ppm) at $pH 9.1$. In the proton nmr spectra, many upfield chemical shifts are observed for imidazole residue. Most significantly, in $DMSO-d_6$ solution containing Ni(II)-AAHNMA, there is a complete disappearance of Ala and His N-H protons, which confirms the coordination of these two peptide nitrogens. The above results suggest that Ni(II) forms complex with this peptide involving the $\alpha-NH_2$, N(3) imidazole, two deprotonated peptide nitrogens, and the COO^- group in a pentacoordinated structure as shown by the arrows in Fig. 7. Subsequent studies of Ni(II)-binding to the NH_2 -terminal 24-residue peptide fragment of HSA by ^{13}C -nmr technique confirmed the above structure²⁰.

Under these circumstances, the results suggest a 1 : 1 complex (Fig. 10).

Fig. 9. ¹H-NMR spectra (220 MHz) of cyclo (Gly-L-Glu-Gly-Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly) in DMSO-d₆. The upper spectrum is of the free peptide, the lower of octapeptide in presence of Zn(II) (1 : 1). The scale is downfield from TMS²².

Fig. 10. The variation of the ¹³C chemical shift as a function of the relative concentration of Zn(II) present. The data were obtained in DMSO-d₆²².

In Table 5, the chemical shifts of ¹H and ¹³C resonances in cyclo-octapeptide are compared with the corresponding resonances observed in the 1 : 1 complex. In the case of protons, the largest chemical shift changes are observed for the proton resonances of the histidine residues and more particularly C(2)H protons. All the NH resonances are unaffected. Thus, the peptide -NH- group does

not participate in coordination. The chemical shifts induced on glutamic acid residue are about 0.1 ppm or less. In the case of ¹³C resonances, the most dramatic changes in chemical shift occur in the histidine residues and especially in the imidazole ring. The three carbon of the imidazole ring, C(2), C(4) and C(5), show a large change in chemical shift upon binding to Zn(II). The two methylenes of the glutamic residue show a large change in chemical shift upon ligating to the metal ion. Both carbons are shifted downfield (Glu C_γ = 0.88 ppm,

TABLE 5—¹³C- AND ¹H-NMR SHIFTS FOR CYCLO-OCTAPEPTIDE AND 1 : 1 Zn(II)-CYCLO-OCTAPEPTIDE IN DMSO-d₆

	¹³ C		¹ H	
	cP8 ^a	cP8-Zn(II)	cP8	cP8-Z(II)
Glu CH ₂ β	31.38	32.07	1.89	1.87
His CH ₂ β	33.72	32.07	2.89	2.97
	34.03		3.02	3.15
Glu CH ₂ γ	35.23	36.11	2.22	2.32
Gly CH ₂	47.88	47.89	3.86	3.86
			3.82	3.82
			3.67	3.67
			3.62	
Glu CH α	57.81	56.81	4.16	4.21
His CH α	58.80	57.89	4.30	4.43
			4.46	4.66
			6.92	7.02
C(5)-H	121.36	125.02 ^b	—	—
	121.80		—	—
C(4)-H	138.98	135.49 ^b	—	—
C(2)-H	140.11	141.31	7.65	8.08
			7.70	
Gly CO	174.55	174.43	—	—
	175.00	174.70	—	—
		174.90	—	—
His CO	176.80	175.76	—	—
	177.41	176.64	—	—
Glu CO	177.66	177.53	—	—
Glu COO ⁻	179.08	181.09	—	—

^a cP8 : cyclo-octapeptide.

^b Linewidth at half-height 60 Hz [C(4)-H] and 36 Hz [C(5)-H].

Glu C_β = 0.69 ppm). The carboxyl resonances from glycine are essentially unaffected upon Zn(II) binding. But the carbonyl atoms of glutamic and the two histidine residues shift upfield -0.13, -1.04 and -0.77 ppm, respectively, upon complexation. The most significant observation is the deshielding effect (Δ = 2.01 ppm). From these observations, it is clear that the largest chemical shifts occur for the two imidazole rings and for the glutamic

Fig. 11. Structure of the Zn(II)-binding to the designed cyclo-octapeptide as deduced from the nmr studies²².

carboxyl group. The results demonstrate that both the imidazoles of the two histidine residues and the carboxyl side chain of the glutamic acid residue of the cyclo-octapeptide are coordinated to Zn(II) as shown in Fig. 11.

Zinc(II)-binding site of carbonic anhydrase :

Carbonic anhydrase is a Zn(II) containing metalloenzyme and the catalytic activity of the enzyme is linked to the presence of Zn(II) ion²⁴. The biologically relevant activity of the enzyme is the reversible hydration of carbon dioxide although it is known to catalyze a variety of hydration reactions, such as the hydration of various aldehydes, and carboxylic, sulfonic and carbonic esters. Zinc(II) in the enzyme is bound to the histidine residues, which in human B isozyme are : His-94, His-96, and His-119²⁵. The coordination geometry about the Zn(II) is distorted tetrahedral with the fourth position occupied by a water molecule.

Considering the known structure of the Zn(II)-binding site of carbonic anhydrase, the simplest possible peptide model which may be proposed for this metal binding site is one which contains three histidyl residues linked in a manner that would enable formation of the base of a tetrahedron when Zn(II) complexation occurs. Similar considerations as those followed in the design of carboxypeptidase a Zn(II)-binding model resulted in the designing of a cyclic heptapeptide molecule : cyclo(Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly)²⁶. Model building by both CPK and Kendrew models indicated that the three histidines of the above cyclic heptapeptide have the ability to interact with the Zn(II) to form a tetrahedral complex.

The cyclic heptapeptide was synthesized from the linear heptapeptide, Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly-OH, which in turn was obtained by coupling of the fragments, viz., BOC-Gly-L-His-Gly-N₂ and L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly-OBzlNO₂ followed by deblocking of amino and carboxyl protecting groups. Conversion of the linear heptapeptide to the azide by treatment with diphenylphosphoryl azide was followed by cyclization in high dilution. The homogeneous material was found to be ninhydrin negative. The nmr spectrum of the material upon integration indicated the proper ratios of various kinds of protons to be expected of the cyclic heptapeptide²⁶.

The metal titration studies show that the magnitude of the chemical shift perturbations induced by Zn(II) increases in increasing metal ion concentration from Zn(II)/peptide ratio 1 : 4 to 1 : 1 ; beyond this ratio, the shift is unaffected. Thus, the cyclic heptapeptide forms a 1 : 1 complex with Zn(II). Similar studies were undertaken by ¹³C-nmr technique. Fig. 12 shows the relationship between the ratio of Zn(II)-peptide to the change in chemical shift of the C(2), C(4) and C(5) imidazole carbons of the cyclic peptide. The change in chemical shift for all the carbons is linear to a ratio of 1 : 1, following which it seems to level off. This result is consistent with a 1 : 1 complex of Zn(II)-cyclopeptide.

Fig. 12. The variations of the ¹³C chemical shift in DMSO-d₆ as a function of the cyclic heptapeptide/Zn ratio²⁶.

The ¹H- and ¹³C-nmr spectra of free cyclic heptapeptide and Zn(II)-bound peptide are shown in Figs. 13 and 14. The chemical shifts of ¹H and ¹³C resonances in cyclopeptide are compared with the

Fig. 13. A portion of the ¹H-nmr spectrum obtained in DMSO-d₆ at 250 MHz showing the resonances of the exchangeable N-H protons and imidazole protons of cyclic heptapeptide (a) and its 1 : 1 complex with Zn(II) (b)²⁶.

Fig. 14. ¹³C-NMR spectra (22.63 MHz) of cyclo(Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly-L-His-Gly) in DMSO-d₆, in the (a) absence and (b) presence of 1:1 Zn(II)²⁺.

corresponding resonances observed in the 1 : 1 complex in Table 6. The changes in the chemical shift of the proton of imidazole are relatively large, indicating that this ring is involved in the complexation. The largest downfield shift occurs for the imidazole N(1)-H proton ($\Delta=1.34$ ppm). The peptide -NH- resonances are clearly observable and almost unaffected. Consequently, none of these nitrogens can serve as a ligand.

three imidazole residues are affected in the same way and suggest that these residues of cyclo-heptapeptide are ligands. Both C(2) and C(5) carbons move downfield ($\Delta=1.71$ and 1.96, 2.54 ppm, respectively) while C(4) moves upfield upon complexation ($\Delta=-1.63$ and -1.85 ppm). Shifts of similar magnitude and sign have been observed for the imidazole residue of histidine when this amino acid residue in a peptide binds to Zn(II)^{5a,57}. There are changes in His C_α and His C_β, which are all neighbours of the imidazole ring. The Gly C_α carbon signals and the Gly carbonyl resonances appear to be unaffected by metal complexation whereas the carbonyl carbon atoms of the three histidine residues move ~ 0.50 ppm upfield on complexation. From these results, we can conclude that the designed cyclic heptapeptide binds a single Zn(II) ion in 1 : 1 complex and that the binding site for Zn(II) is the N(3) nitrogen of the three imidazole residues as shown in Fig. 15.

TABLE 6—¹³C- AND ¹H-NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS FOR CYCLO-HEPTAPEPTIDE AND 1 : 1 Zn(II)-CYCLO-HEPTAPEPTIDE IN DMSO-d₆.

	¹³ C		¹ H	
	cP7 ^a	Zn(II)-cP7	cP7	Zn(II)-cP7
His CH _β	32.25	31.40	2.93	3.11
Gly CH _α	46.81	46.87	3.47	3.55
	47.00	47.04	3.60	3.74
His CH _α	57.21	56.30	4.36	4.52
	57.67	57.02	4.48	—
C(5)-H	121.45	123.41	6.79	6.90
C(4)-H	136.67	135.04	—	—
	137.25	135.40	—	—
C(2)-H	138.49	140.20	7.54	8.16
	—	—	7.59	8.28
N(1)-H	—	—	11.88	13.22
	—	—	—	—
Gly CO	173.63	173.80	—	—
	173.93	173.90	—	—
His CO	175.42	174.06	—	—
	176.13	175.10	—	—
	—	175.42	—	—
—	175.87	—	—	

^a cP7, cyclo-heptapeptide.

By addition of one equivalent of Zn(II) to the peptide, the imidazole residue is the most affected as shown by the ¹³C-nmr spectra. The C(2), C(4) and C(5) carbon resonances of this group are dramatically affected and show a very large change in chemical shift after complexation. In fact, all

Fig. 15. Structure of the Zn(II)-binding to the designed cyclic heptapeptide as deduced from the nmr studies.

Conclusion :

The results discussed above confirm the concept of molecular design to mimic the metal-binding sites of biological macromolecules²². However, several interesting facts have emerged from these studies. In the investigations of the Cu(II)-transport site of HSA, we initially designed two peptides, GGH and GGHNMA. Both the peptides demonstrated a remarkable similarity with the Cu(II)-transport site of HSA. But it was not until the native sequence peptide AAHNMA was synthesized and the Cu(II)-binding studies were carried out did we recognize the full implication of the carboxyl side chain of the NH₂-terminal aspartyl residue of HSA. Extensive chemical and physical studies with the native HSA molecule failed to detect the involvement of the carboxyl group in the coordination of Cu(II). The same holds true with the Ni(II)-transport site of HSA. Although these experiments helped in the structural elucidation of the Cu(II)-transport site of HSA, the functional aspects of this site are still unclear. It is possible that some residues which may not be directly bonded to the metal, yet close enough, could influence the dynamics of the Cu(II)-transport. In designing models for the Zn(II) binding sites of carboxypeptidase and carbonic anhydrase, it is clear that the cyclic peptides afforded both the rigidity and the ligand binding geometry of the native metal binding sites. In these models, too, the functional aspects of the metal binding sites are not considered and hence no catalytic activity of the enzyme can be expected in these molecules. One should also bear in mind that in none of these models does the native microenvironment around the metal binding site appear. Thus, one must use caution to interpret the model studies in relation to defining the native metal binding sites. However, peptide molecules belong to an important class of models to probe the metal binding sites and a careful analysis of the results should provide critical information about the structure of the metal-binding sites of proteins and enzymes.

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References

- I. M. KLOTZ and H. G. CURME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 939.
- I. M. KOLTHOFF and B. R. WILLEFORD, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 5673.
- B. SARKAR and Y. WIGFIELD, *Cand. J. Biochem.*, 1968, 46, 601.
- T. PETERS, Jr., *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1960, 39, 546.
- E. BRESLOW, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1964, 239, 3252.
- T. PETERS, Jr. and F. A. BLUMENSTOCK, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1967, 242, 1574.
- D. W. APPLETON and B. SARKAR, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1971, 246, 5040.
- J. W. DIXON and B. SARKAR, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1974, 249, 5872.
- S. LAU, T. P. A. KRUCK and B. SARKAR, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1974, 249, 5878.
- S. LAU and B. SARKAR, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton*, 1981, 491.
- T. P. A. KRUCK, S. LAU and B. SARKAR, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1976, 54, 1300.
- K. S. N. IYER, S. LAU, S. H. LAURIE and B. SARKAR, *Biochem. J.*, 1978, 169, 61.
- B. SARKAR and T. P. A. KRUCK, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1973, 51, 3541.
- B. SARKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 117.
- N. CAMERMAN, A. CAMERMAN and B. SARKAR, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1976, 54, 1309.
- G. RAKHIT and B. SARKAR, *J. Inorganic Biochem.*, 1981, 15, 233.
- B. SARKAR, V. RENUGOPALAKRISHNAM, T. P. A. KRUCK and S. LAU in "Environmental Effects on Molecular Structure and Properties", (Ed.) B. PULLMAN, D. Reidel Publishing Co., Dordrecht-Holland, 1976, p. 165.
- J.-P. LAUSSAC and B. SARKAR, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1980, 255, 7563.
- B. SARKAR, J.-P. LAUSSAC and S. LAU in "Biological Aspects of Metals and Metal-Related Diseases", (Ed.) B. SARKAR, Raven Press, New York, 1983, in press.
- B. SARKAR, "Proceedings of the Nobel Symposium on Inorganic Biochemistry", Sweden, 1982, p. 26.
- B. SARKAR, "Life Chemistry Reports", Oxford, 1983, in press.
- B. SARKAR and J.-P. LAUSSAC, "Proceedings of the International Conference on Coordination Chemistry", Hungary, 1982, p. 53.
- M. LUCASSEN and B. SARKAR, *J. Toxicol. & Environ. Hlth.*, 1979, 5, 897.
- J. D. GLENNON and B. SARKAR, *Biochem. J.*, 1982, 203, 15.
- J. D. GLENNON and B. SARKAR, *Biochem. J.*, 1982, 203, 25.
- J.-P. LAUSSAC and B. SARKAR, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1980, 58, 2055.
- R. PIRAS and B. L. VALLEE, *Biochemistry*, 1967, 6, 348.
- B. L. VALLEE and J. F. RIORDAN, "Brookhaven Symposium in Biology", 1968, 21, 91.
- W. N. LIPSCOMB, J. A. HARTSUCH, G. N. REERE, JR., F. A. QUIOCHO, P. H. BETHGE, M. L. LUDWIG, T. A. STEITZ, H. MUIRHEAD and J. A. COPPOLA, "Brookhaven Symposium in Biology", 1968, 21, 24.
- R. A. BRADSHAW, L. H. ERICSON, K. A. WALSH and H. NEURATH, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1969, 63, 406.
- S. LAU and B. SARKAR, *Proc. Cand. Fed.*, 1971, 14, 33.
- S. LAU and B. SARKAR, *Proc. Cand. Fed.*, 1973, 16, 97.
- K. S. IYER, J.-P. LAUSSAC, S. LAU and B. SARKAR, *Intl. J. Peptide and Protein Res.*, 1981, 17, 549.
- D. KEILIN and T. MANN, *Biochem. J.*, 1940, 34, 1163.
- K. K. KANNAN, B. NOTSTRAND, K. FRIDBORG, S. LÖVGREN, A. OHLSSON and M. PETEF, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1975, 72, 51.
- K. S. IYER, J.-P. LAUSSAC and B. SARKAR, *Intl. J. Peptide and Protein Res.*, 1981, 18, 468.
- H. LAKUSTA, C. M. DEBER and B. SARKAR, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1980, 58, 757.
- B. SARKAR in "Metal Ligand Interaction in Organic and Biochemistry", (Ed.) B. PULLMAN, D. Reidel, Dordrecht-Holland, 1977, p. 193.